

Figure S7. Number of differentially expressed transcripts (DETs) with a fold-change greater than 2 (FC>2) identified in each pairwise comparison between embryo developmental stages. Up-regulated and down-regulated transcripts are shown in red and green bars, respectively. The number of total DETs in each pairwise comparison is shown below.

Table S7. Differentially expressed TFs (FC>2), related to developmental process, detected in the pairwise comparisons between consecutive stages during embryo development. Positive values for fold-changes (FC) in each comparison indicate up-regulated transcripts, negative values indicate down-regulated transcripts.

Transcript ID	FC	At locus	At name	At annotation
Pairwise comparison E1/E2				
isotig68230	99	AT3G01470.1	HAT5	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein HAT5
isotig72228	99	AT3G58190.1	LBD29	LOB domain-containing protein 29
isotig95662	99	AT2G27230.1	LHW	Transcription factor LHW
isotig90693	99	AT3G54560.1	H2AV	Histone H2A variant 1
isotig48941	5.05	AT1G71830.1	SERK1	Somatic embryogenesis receptor kinase 1 LRR receptor-like serine/threonine-protein kinase ERL2
isotig58389	4.86	AT5G07180.1	ERL2	
isotig44842	3.63	AT5G12330.2	LRP1	Protein LATERAL ROOT PRIMORDIUM 1
isotig39138	3.57	AT5G39660.1	CDF2	Cyclic dof factor 2
isotig59598	3.52	AT1G69780.1	ATHB-13	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein ATHB-13
isotig72491	3.29	AT3G58850.1	PAR2	Transcription factor PAR2
isotig61680	3.26	AT3G01470.1	HAT5	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein HAT5
isotig59974	3.19	AT3G57230.1	AGL16	Agamous-like MADS-box protein AGL16
isotig33091	3.18	AT1G14920.1	GAI	DELLA protein GAI
isotig39479	3.15	AT2G21660.1	RBG7	Glycine-rich RNA-binding protein 7
isotig27037	3.07	AT2G35060.1	POT11	Potassium transporter 11
isotig64424	2.7	AT3G58850.1	PAR2	Transcription factor PAR2
isotig56444	2.60	AT3G12810.1	PIE1	Protein PHOTOPERIOD-INDEPENDENT EARLY FLOWERING 1
isotig43989	2.53	AT1G26780.1	MYB117	myb domain protein 117
isotig56396	2.47	AT3G51550.1	FER	Receptor-like protein kinase FERONIA
isotig61074	2.44	AT1G18750.1	AGL65	AGAMOUS-like 65
isotig40387	2.42	AT1G52150.1	ATHB-15	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein ATHB-15
isotig58190	2.42	AT1G32240.1	KAN2	Probable transcription factor KAN2
isotig58719	2.38	AT4G04885.1	PCFS4	Polyadenylation and cleavage factor homolog 4
isotig61477	2.36	AT1G06040.1	BBX24	B-box zinc finger protein 24
isotig82050	2.3	AT2G27230.1	LHW	Transcription factor LHW
isotig38826	2.19	AT4G18770.1	MYB98	Transcription factor MYB98
isotig39222	2.15	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig34304	-99	AT1G52150.2	ATHB-15	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein ATHB-15
isotig39945	-5.57	AT3G24650.1	ABI3	B3 domain-containing transcription factor ABI3
isotig37162	-4.92	AT3G24140.1	FAMA	Transcription factor FAMA
isotig38812	-4.34	AT3G59420.1	ACR4	Serine/threonine-protein kinase-like protein ACR4
isotig35426	-4.18	AT2G42560.1		LEA domain-containing protein Ethylene-responsive transcription factor
isotig63058	-3.34	AT2G40220.1	ABI4	ABI4
isotig47939	-3.34	AT1G52880.1	NAC18	NAC domain-containing protein 18

isotig63714	-3.24	AT1G77450.1	anac32	NAC domain containing protein 32
isotig63554	-3.10	AT2G40220.1	ABI4	Ethylene-responsive transcription factor ABI4
isotig94895	-3.1	AT1G19220.1	ARF19	Auxin response factor 19
isotig65664	-2.96	AT1G20930.1	CDKB2-2	Cyclin-dependent kinase B2-2
isotig63792	-2.75	AT1G01720.1	NAC2	NAC domain-containing protein 2
isotig41211	-2.72	AT1G51190.1	PLT2	AP2-like ethylene-responsive transcription factor PLT2
isotig33112	-2.60	AT1G05230.3	HDG2	Homeobox-leucine zipper protein HDG2
isotig61378	-2.53	AT3G57670.1	WIP2	Zinc finger protein WIP2
isotig07912	-2.41	AT4G30270.1	XTH24	Xyloglucan ndotransglucosylase/hydrolase protein 24
isotig11918	-2.12	AT4G31920.1	ARR1	Two-component response regulator ARR10
isotig81524	-2.09	AT2G21660.1	RBG7	Glycine-rich RNA-binding protein 7
isotig19043	-2.07	AT3G08970.1	ERDJ3A	DnaJ protein ERDJ3A
isotig84240	-2.06	AT2G21660.1	RBG7	Glycine-rich RNA-binding protein 7
isotig62912	-2.04	AT3G54180.1	CDKB1-1	Cyclin-dependent kinase B1-1

Pairwise comparison E2/E3D0

isotig71762	2.09	AT1G51450.1	TRO	Protein TRAUCO
isotig50769	-2.14	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig25191	-2.14	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2

Pairwise comparison E3D0/E4

isotig101628	99	AT5G62000.1	ARF2	Auxin response factor 2
isotig89845	99	AT4G32551.1	LUG	Transcriptional corepressor LEUNIG
isotig50769	4.46	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig13246	3.91	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig25191	3.47	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig04574	3.36	AT5G09970.1	CYP78A7	Cytochrome P450 78A7
isotig65385	3.21	AT1G52880.1	NAC018	NAC domain-containing protein 18
isotig67346	3.14	AT5G15540.1	EMB2773	PHD finger family protein
isotig61540	2.63	AT3G15510.1	ATNAC2	NAC domain containing protein 2
isotig18917	2.41	AT3G04070.2	anac047	NAC domain containing protein 47
isotig45225	2.35	AT2G30130.1	LBD12	LOB domain-containing protein 12
isotig71987	-99	AT1G03120.1	ATRAB28	responsive to abscisic acid 28
isotig71994	-99	AT2G01500.1	WOX6	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 6
isotig71508	-4.82	AT2G30420.1	ETC2	MYB-like transcription factor ETC2
isotig39159	-2.89	AT1G03120.1	ATRAB28	responsive to abscisic acid 28
isotig37135	-2.87	AT4G08150.1	KNAT1	Homeobox protein knotted-1-like 1
isotig59371	-2.54	AT5G09970.1	CYP78A7	Cytochrome P450 78A7
isotig59013	-2.40	AT3G13960.1	GRF5	Growth-regulating factor 5
isotig63158	-2.40	AT1G26870.1	ANAC009	NAC domain transcriptional regulator superfamily protein
isotig60977	-2.38	AT5G61850.1	LFY	Protein LEAFY
isotig09216	-2.11	AT5G54380.1	THE1	Receptor-like protein kinase THESEUS 1

Pairwise comparison E3DO/E3SU

isotig25191	5.57	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig50769	4.57	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig18917	4.09	AT3G04070.2	anac047	NAC domain containing protein 47
isotig57427	2.73	AT5G63090.2	LOB	Protein LATERAL ORGAN BOUNDARIES
isotig14005	2.59	AT1G65910.1	anac028	NAC domain containing protein 28 Ethylene-responsive transcription factor
isotig62449	2.51	AT2G40220.1	ABI4	ABI4
isotig13246	2.43	AT5G59340.1	WOX2	WUSCHEL-related homeobox 2
isotig61540	2.41	AT3G15510.1	ATNAC2	NAC domain containing protein 2
isotig65385	2.32	AT1G52880.1	NAC018	NAC domain-containing protein 18
isotig65643	2.17	AT3G04070.2	anac047	NAC domain containing protein 47
isotig71508	-3.40	AT2G30420.1	ETC2	MYB-like transcription factor ETC2
isotig59371	-2.54	AT5G09970.1	CYP78A7	Cytochrome P450 78A7
